

Fluorescence in Organic Compounds.

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Fluorescence in organic compounds has always been attributed to a fundamental property of the molecules themselves. But an interesting phenomenon has been observed by the present author, namely, that many of the fluorescent substances when subjected to an elaborate and exhaustive process of purification, temporarily or permanently lose their fluorescence. The following eight such compounds have up to this time been prepared in a non-fluorescent condition: quinine, resacetophenone, anthracene, methylacridine, eosine, fluorescein, anthranilic acid and dicyanoquinol. In the case of fluorescein, the fluorescence does not disappear altogether but is diminished to a very considerable extent, while in other cases the disappearance is complete. It is interesting to note that most of the compounds regain their fluorescence on being kept exposed to the vitiated atmosphere of the laboratory for some time, especially on heating them to the melting point of the respective substances. The following table will summarise the results obtained during the last seven years.

Name of substance.*	No. of times crystallised.	Total time required in the process.	Yield.	Change in m.p.	Period of non-fluorescent stage.
Quinine ...	21	3 months	1.2%	2°	25-30 days.
Resacetophenone...	18	5 days	2.9	2°	3½-4 months.
Anthracene ...	22	4 months	2.6	2°	6-7 days.
Methylacridine ...	22	6 months	0.7	5°	50-60 days.
Eosine ...	35	14 months	0.3	—	1½-2 years.
Fluorescein ...	58	3½ years	0.03	—	2½-3 years.
Anthranilic acid ...	18	2 months	1.2	1°	Indefinite.
Dicyanoquinol ...	38	14 months	1.1	9°	Indefinite.

* The substances after purification were analysed; the analytical data agreed with the theoretical values.

Although only eight compounds could be purified to a condition of non-fluorescence during seven years, yet further attempts are being made to add to the list so that they may not prove themselves rather the exception than the rule. The data that have yet been obtained are too insufficient to arrive at any generalisation of the problem.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Quinine.—50 G. of pure quinine nitrate in 1% solution in water were maintained at 45° in a thermostat for 144 hours while a slow stream of carbon dioxide was passed through the solution. The free base was then precipitated by ammonia and crystallised from dilute alcohol with the addition of activated charcoal and kaolin, 21 times. Finally the base was obtained in a condition in which it did not show any visible fluorescence in alcoholic or acid solution; m.p. 176°. The fluorescence gradually reappears on allowing the substance to remain exposed to the air for some days.

Resacetophenone.—It was crystallised from hot dilute hydrochloric acid (5%) 18 times with the addition of activated charcoal, when finally it was obtained in the form of colourless glistening prisms melting at 142°. These dissolved in alcohol to a colourless, and in dilute sodium hydroxide to a pale yellow solution, which are entirely devoid of any fluorescence. On allowing the substance to remain exposed to the air it gradually turns pink in colour and the fluorescence also gradually reverts. The process is very much hastened by heating the substance to the melting point.

Anthracene.—Merck's pure resublimed anthracene (150 g.) was heated in an autoclave with water (250 c.c.) at 220° for about 12 hours. The substance was then taken out, boiled with dilute sodium hydroxide solution, filtered, washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and water and finally sublimed and resublimed in steam at 180-190°, 12 times. Finally it was crystallised 10 times from glacial acetic acid containing traces of sulphur dioxide and obtained in snow white flakes melting at 215°, and entirely devoid of any blue fluorescence. The fluorescence however reappears *very quickly* in this substance specially on exposure to the vitiated atmosphere of the laboratory or by treatment with mild oxidising agents, such as, dilute nitric acid, hydrogen peroxide, potassium persulphate and so on. It also reappears on heating the substance near its melting point for a short time.

Methylacridine.—140 G. of 9-methylacridine were dissolved in dilute sulphuric acid and the solution treated with dilute barium chloride solution until barium sulphate was no longer precipitated. The resultant precipitate carried down with it much of colouring matter of the solution. The filtered solution was then treated with dilute ammonia when the methylacridine was reprecipitated. This was again dissolved in dilute sulphuric acid and the above process was repeated 9 times. The methylacridine was then dissolved in 70% alcohol and refluxed on the water-bath with kaolin and activated charcoal for about three hours. The filtered solution on dilution with cold water formed a milky emulsion which was dissolved on passing a current of sulphur dioxide through the solution. Finally on addition of dilute ammonia, the methylacridine was precipitated in fine pale yellow glistening prisms which were filtered off and recrystallised 13 times from dilute alcohol containing traces of stannous chloride. It was thus obtained in colourless prisms with silky lustre which on drying in an atmosphere of hydrogen melted at 118° , and were entirely devoid of any fluorescence. The substance was very liable to regain its blue fluorescence by oxidation in air or by treatment with any chemical oxidising agent whereby it also loses its colourlessness and assumes a pale yellow tint. The blue fluorescence also at once reappears on subliming the substance under ordinary conditions.

Eosin.—The purest available sample of Merck's eosin was dissolved in water and the free acid precipitated by the addition of dilute hydrochloric acid. This was then crystallised alternately from alcohol and acetic acid 35 times with the addition of small quantities of active charcoal. The sample of tetrabromoresorcinolphthalein thus obtained was then converted into the ammonium salt by passing a slow stream of dry ammonia over it contained in a tube, mixed with pure hydrogen. The eosin was thus obtained in glistening prisms with steel-blue metallic reflex, which dissolved in water with a beautiful pink colour entirely devoid of any fluorescence. The fluorescence however reappears in the solution by keeping it exposed to the air for two days or by passing a current of air through it. The dry solid substance however can be preserved indefinitely without regaining fluorescence, if it is kept in an air-tight vessel in the dark.

Fluorescein.—The eosin as prepared in the above instance was then reduced in 80% alcoholic solution with pure zinc and hydrochloric acid. The reduction was complete when a sample of the

substance on precipitation from alcoholic solution with water was found to be free from bromine. The fluorescein thus obtained, after 10 crystallisations from alcohol, was converted into fluorescein by oxidation in 90% acetic acid solution with the calculated quantity of freshly precipitated manganese dioxide (prepared by quantitative precipitation of pure potassium permanganate in aqueous solution with alcohol). The solution was filtered and the fluorescein precipitated from it by the addition of a saturated solution of sodium acetate. It was then filtered, washed, dried and dissolved in absolute alcohol and precipitated by petroleum ether and the last process repeated 12 times. The fluorescein was thus obtained as an orange crystalline powder which dissolved in dilute alkalis with a very pale greenish-yellow fluorescence. As a matter of fact the intensity of fluorescence was found to be reduced by nearly 95%. It could not however be obtained in a condition entirely devoid of any fluorescence. The full intensity of fluorescence reappears when the substance is heated at 200° for ten minutes, or when through the alkaline solution a current of air is passed for about 12 hours. The dry substance can however be preserved indefinitely without regaining the original fluorescence if kept in an air-tight vessel in the dark.

Anthranilic Acid.—Lead salt of the acid was prepared in the usual manner and decomposed in alcoholic suspension with hydrogen sulphide. The precipitated lead sulphide was filtered off and from the filtrate the acid was regenerated by the addition of water. This process was repeated 17 times. Finally the acid was crystallised from hot water with addition of activated charcoal 12 times, when it was obtained in colourless leaflets which dissolved in acids, alkalis or organic solvents without a trace of fluorescence; m.p. 145°. The substance does not regain fluorescence unless it is kept at the melting point for half an hour.

Dicyanoquinol.—This was crystallised from hot water containing traces of sulphurous acid and also with the addition of small quantities of activated charcoal 38 times. Thus obtained it was entirely devoid of any fluorescence. Colourless silky needles, melting at 239° with decomposition. The substance does not regain fluorescence under any condition.

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